

Structure report: (2E)-1-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-3-(3-methylthiophen-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one

D'Silva E D

Department of Physics
Center for Post Graduate Studies and Research,
St. Philomena College, Puttur, India
deepak.dsilva@gmail.com

The compound (2E)-1-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-3-(3-methylthiophen-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one was synthesized by the reaction of 3-methylthiophene-2-carbaldehyde with 3,4-dimethylacetophenone. The structure of the synthesized compound was characterized by subjecting it to single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. The compound crystallizes in the monoclinic crystal class with space group $P 1 21/c 1$. The cell parameters are $a = 7.1331(4) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 28.5501(11) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 7.2354(5) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 116.873(8)^\circ$, $V = 1314.36(14) \text{ \AA}^3$ and $Z = 4$.

Introduction

Chalcones are precursor of various natural products such as flavonoids, isoflavanoids and key intermediates for synthesis of various heterocyclic scaffolds [1]. Chalcone consists of two aromatic rings joined together by a three carbon α, β -unsaturated carbonyl system. These compounds have broad range of biological activities such as anticancer, antimalarial activity, anti-TB activity, antiviral, antibacterial, antifilarial activity etc [2]. A vast number of naturally occurring chalcones are polyhydroxylated in the aryl rings. The radical quenching properties of the phenol groups present in many chalcones have raised interest in using the compounds or chalcone rich plant extracts as drugs or food preservatives [3]. Chalcones are finding applications as organic non-linear optical materials (NLO) due to their good SHG conversion efficiencies and higher order nonlinear optical properties [4]. Owing to the importance of these chalcones, this new chalcone (2E)-1-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-3-(3-methylthiophen-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one was synthesized and its crystal structure is reported.

Experimental

The compound (2E)-1-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-3-(3-methylthiophen-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one was synthesized by the condensation of 3-methylthiophene-2-carbaldehyde (0.01 mol) with 3,4-dimethylacetophenone (0.01 mol) in methanol (60 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of sodium hydroxide solution (5 ml, 30%) [5]. After stirring (6 h), the contents of the flask were poured into ice-cold water (500 ml) and left to stand for 5 h. The resulting

crude solid was filtered and dried. The precipitated compound was recrystallized from methanol.

The single crystal X-ray diffraction data was collected on Bruker Kappa Apex using Apex2 software package [6]. The radiation used was graphite monochromatic MoK α radiation. All the data were corrected for Lorentz factor and empirical absorption. The structure was solved by direct method and all the non-hydrogen atoms and hydrogen atoms were found in difference electron density maps. The atomic coordinates and anisotropic temperature factors for non-hydrogen atoms were refined by the full matrix least square method using SHELXTL program package [7].

The molecule exhibits an E configuration with respect to the C10=C11 double bond with the C9—C10—C11—C12 torsion angle being $-178.6(2)^\circ$. The bond lengths and bond angles are found to have normal values [8]. The dihedral angle between the benzene and the thiophene ring are 27.79° , indicating that they are non-planar.

In the crystal structure, the molecules are stacked along the *b* axis. Along each axis the adjacent molecules are inverted and arranged in head-to-tail fashion. The parallel molecules between two axes aligned in the same direction. The crystal packing is consolidated by inter molecular C—H $\cdots$ O and C—H $\cdots$ H hydrogen bonding interactions.

Special Details :

Geometry: All e.s.d.'s (except the e.s.d. in the dihedral angle between two l.s. planes) are estimated using the full covariance matrix. The cell e.s.d.'s are taken into account individually in the estimation of e.s.d.'s in distances, angles and torsion angles; correlations between e.s.d.'s in cell parameters are only used when they are defined by crystal symmetry. An approximate (isotropic) treatment of cell e.s.d.'s is used for estimating e.s.d.'s involving l.s. planes.

Refinement: Refinement of F^2 against ALL reflections. The weighted R-factor wR and goodness of fit S are based on F^2 , conventional R-factors R are based on F , with F set to zero for negative F^2 . The threshold expression of $F^2 > \sigma(F^2)$ is used only for calculating R-factors(gt) etc. and is not relevant to the choice of reflections for refinement. R-factors based on F^2 are statistically about twice as large as those based on F , and R-factors based on ALL data will be even larger.

Fig. 1 Reaction Scheme for the title compound

Fig. 2 Molecular structure of the title compound, showing the atom labeling scheme and 50% probability displacement ellipsoids.

Fig. 3 Packing diagram of the title compound, viewed down the *b* axis. Dashed lines indicate intermolecular bond interaction

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement

Empirical formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅
Formula weight	256.35
Temperature	110(2) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P 1 2 ₁ /c 1
Unit cell dimensions	a = 7.1331(4) Å $\alpha = 90^\circ$. b = 28.5501(11) Å $\beta = 116.873(8)^\circ$. c = 7.2354(5) Å $\gamma = 90^\circ$.
Volume	1314.36(14) Å ³
Z	4
Density (calculated)	1.295 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.231 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	544
Crystal size	0.46 x 0.34 x 0.14 mm ³
Theta range for data collection	4.77 to 32.65°.
Index ranges	-10 ≤ h ≤ 10, -41 ≤ k ≤ 36, -10 ≤ l ≤ 9
Reflections collected	13232
Independent reflections	4397 [R(int) = 0.1711]
Completeness to theta = 25.00°	99.1 %
Absorption correction	Semi-empirical from equivalents
Max. and min. transmission	1.00000 and 0.78949
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²
Data / restraints / parameters	4397 / 0 / 166
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.151
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	R1 = 0.0833, wR2 = 0.1625
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.1329, wR2 = 0.1759
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.567 and -0.395 e.Å ⁻³

Supplementary materials

Table 2. Atomic coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and equivalent isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$). $U(\text{eq})$ is defined as one third of the trace of the orthogonalized U^{ij} tensor.

	x	y	z	U(eq)
S	721(1)	2210(1)	1923(1)	24(1)
O	6320(3)	3610(1)	3452(3)	28(1)
C(1)	3306(3)	4057(1)	2812(3)	14(1)
C(2)	4215(3)	4463(1)	2476(3)	13(1)
C(3)	3358(3)	4904(1)	2378(3)	13(1)
C(4)	1533(3)	4948(1)	2648(3)	14(1)
C(5)	610(3)	4541(1)	2945(3)	15(1)
C(6)	1463(3)	4099(1)	3013(3)	17(1)
C(7)	4389(3)	5331(1)	2021(4)	17(1)
C(8)	614(3)	5424(1)	2637(4)	18(1)
C(9)	4460(3)	3602(1)	3052(4)	18(1)
C(10)	3316(3)	3159(1)	2807(4)	19(1)
C(11)	4325(4)	2746(1)	3094(4)	19(1)
C(12)	3400(3)	2287(1)	2863(4)	17(1)
C(13)	4443(3)	1861(1)	3337(4)	20(1)
C(14)	6761(4)	1799(1)	4173(5)	35(1)
C(15)	3022(4)	1479(1)	2937(4)	21(1)
C(16)	979(4)	1615(1)	2173(4)	23(1)

Table 3. Bond lengths [$\text{\AA}$] and angles [$^\circ$]

S-C(16)	1.711(2)	C(3)-C(4)	1.407(3)
S-C(12)	1.729(2)	C(3)-C(7)	1.506(3)
O-C(9)	1.224(3)	C(4)-C(5)	1.399(3)
C(1)-C(6)	1.392(3)	C(4)-C(8)	1.506(3)
C(1)-C(2)	1.402(3)	C(5)-C(6)	1.393(3)
C(1)-C(9)	1.504(3)	C(5)-H(5A)	0.9500
C(2)-C(3)	1.387(3)	C(6)-H(6A)	0.9500
C(2)-H(2A)	0.9500	C(7)-H(7A)	0.9800

C(7)-H(7B)	0.9800	C(6)-C(5)-H(5A)	119.0
C(7)-H(7C)	0.9800	C(4)-C(5)-H(5A)	119.0
C(8)-H(8A)	0.9800	C(1)-C(6)-C(5)	119.59(17)
C(8)-H(8B)	0.9800	C(1)-C(6)-H(6A)	120.2
C(8)-H(8C)	0.9800	C(5)-C(6)-H(6A)	120.2
C(9)-C(10)	1.473(3)	C(3)-C(7)-H(7A)	109.5
C(10)-C(11)	1.347(3)	C(3)-C(7)-H(7B)	109.5
C(10)-H(10A)	0.9500	H(7A)-C(7)-H(7B)	109.5
C(11)-C(12)	1.441(3)	C(3)-C(7)-H(7C)	109.5
C(11)-H(11A)	0.9500	H(7A)-C(7)-H(7C)	109.5
C(12)-C(13)	1.387(3)	H(7B)-C(7)-H(7C)	109.5
C(13)-C(15)	1.427(3)	C(4)-C(8)-H(8A)	109.5
C(13)-C(14)	1.492(3)	C(4)-C(8)-H(8B)	109.5
C(14)-H(14A)	0.9800	H(8A)-C(8)-H(8B)	109.5
C(14)-H(14B)	0.9800	C(4)-C(8)-H(8C)	109.5
C(14)-H(14C)	0.9800	H(8A)-C(8)-H(8C)	109.5
C(15)-C(16)	1.360(3)	H(8B)-C(8)-H(8C)	109.5
C(15)-H(15A)	0.9500	O-C(9)-C(10)	121.80(18)
C(16)-H(16A)	0.9500	O-C(9)-C(1)	119.29(17)
C(16)-S-C(12)	92.15(10)	C(10)-C(9)-C(1)	118.91(18)
C(6)-C(1)-C(2)	118.59(17)	C(11)-C(10)-C(9)	120.3(2)
C(6)-C(1)-C(9)	123.81(17)	C(11)-C(10)-H(10A)	119.8
C(2)-C(1)-C(9)	117.51(17)	C(9)-C(10)-H(10A)	119.8
C(3)-C(2)-C(1)	122.10(18)	C(10)-C(11)-C(12)	126.3(2)
C(3)-C(2)-H(2A)	118.9	C(10)-C(11)-H(11A)	116.9
C(1)-C(2)-H(2A)	118.9	C(12)-C(11)-H(11A)	116.9
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	119.31(17)	C(13)-C(12)-C(11)	127.03(19)
C(2)-C(3)-C(7)	120.39(18)	C(13)-C(12)-S	111.10(15)
C(4)-C(3)-C(7)	120.29(17)	C(11)-C(12)-S	121.87(15)
C(5)-C(4)-C(3)	118.38(17)	C(12)-C(13)-C(15)	111.58(19)
C(5)-C(4)-C(8)	121.01(19)	C(12)-C(13)-C(14)	125.17(19)
C(3)-C(4)-C(8)	120.61(17)	C(15)-C(13)-C(14)	123.25(19)
C(6)-C(5)-C(4)	121.99(18)	C(13)-C(14)-H(14A)	109.5

C(13)-C(14)-H(14B)	109.5	C(16)-C(15)-H(15A)	123.3
H(14A)-C(14)-H(14B)	109.5	C(13)-C(15)-H(15A)	123.3
C(13)-C(14)-H(14C)	109.5	C(15)-C(16)-S	111.77(15)
H(14A)-C(14)-H(14C)	109.5	C(15)-C(16)-H(16A)	124.1
H(14B)-C(14)-H(14C)	109.5	S-C(16)-H(16A)	124.1
C(16)-C(15)-C(13)	13.39(18)		
Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms			

Table 4. Anisotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$). The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2 \pi^2 [h^2 a^{*2} U^{11} + \dots + 2 h k a^* b^* U^{12}]$

	U^{11}	U^{22}	U^{33}	U^{23}	U^{13}	U^{12}
S	18(1)	16(1)	33(1)	3(1)	7(1)	1(1)
O	17(1)	18(1)	40(1)	1(1)	5(1)	1(1)
C(1)	13(1)	14(1)	11(1)	0(1)	1(1)	-2(1)
C(2)	10(1)	17(1)	8(1)	0(1)	1(1)	-1(1)
C(3)	14(1)	14(1)	9(1)	0(1)	2(1)	-2(1)
C(4)	14(1)	16(1)	9(1)	-1(1)	2(1)	0(1)
C(5)	11(1)	22(1)	11(1)	-1(1)	4(1)	-3(1)
C(6)	18(1)	15(1)	12(1)	0(1)	4(1)	-6(1)
C(7)	18(1)	14(1)	16(1)	0(1)	7(1)	-4(1)
C(8)	18(1)	19(1)	14(1)	-2(1)	4(1)	3(1)
C(9)	18(1)	14(1)	16(1)	1(1)	2(1)	-1(1)
C(10)	17(1)	15(1)	19(1)	2(1)	4(1)	-2(1)
C(11)	21(1)	15(1)	20(1)	1(1)	7(1)	-2(1)
C(12)	15(1)	15(1)	17(1)	1(1)	5(1)	-1(1)
C(13)	21(1)	16(1)	23(1)	0(1)	10(1)	1(1)
C(14)	20(1)	27(1)	56(2)	1(1)	17(1)	1(1)
C(15)	26(1)	13(1)	23(1)	-2(1)	12(1)	-1(1)
C(16)	23(1)	14(1)	30(1)	-2(1)	10(1)	-4(1)

Table 5. Hydrogen coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$)

	x	y	z	U(eg)
H(2A)	5458	4435	2311	16
H(5A)	-636	4568	3106	18
H(6A)	791	3828	3196	20
H(7A)	5589	5235	1795	25
H(7B)	4877	5536	3236	25
H(7C)	3372	5500	799	25
H(8A)	-649	5388	2836	27
H(8B)	244	5578	1307	27
H(8C)	1650	5614	3762	27
H(10A)	1859	3164	2445	22
H(11A)	5788	2758	3486	23
H(14A)	7353	2069	3783	52
H(14B)	7050	1513	3600	52
H(14C)	7402	1775	5687	52
H(15A)	3458	1161	3181	25
H(16A)	-165	1405	1820	28

Table 6. Torsion angles [$^\circ$]

C(6)-C(1)-C(2)-C(3)	1.2(3)
C(9)-C(1)-C(2)-C(3)	-175.42(19)
C(1)-C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	0.8(3)
C(1)-C(2)-C(3)-C(7)	179.81(19)
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	-1.9(3)
C(7)-C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	179.09(18)
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)-C(8)	177.48(19)
C(7)-C(3)-C(4)-C(8)	-1.5(3)
C(3)-C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	1.1(3)
C(8)-C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	-178.3(2)
C(2)-C(1)-C(6)-C(5)	-2.1(3)

C(9)-C(1)-C(6)-C(5)	174.3(2)
C(4)-C(5)-C(6)-C(1)	1.0(3)
C(6)-C(1)-C(9)-O	-158.8(2)
C(2)-C(1)-C(9)-O	17.6(3)
C(6)-C(1)-C(9)-C(10)	20.9(3)
C(2)-C(1)-C(9)-C(10)	-162.63(19)
O-C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	2.4(4)
C(1)-C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	-177.4(2)
C(9)-C(10)-C(11)-C(12)	-178.6(2)
C(10)-C(11)-C(12)-C(13)	-173.5(2)
C(10)-C(11)-C(12)-S	6.2(4)
C(16)-S-C(12)-C(13)	0.40(19)
C(16)-S-C(12)-C(11)	-179.3(2)
C(11)-C(12)-C(13)-C(15)	179.2(2)
S-C(12)-C(13)-C(15)	-0.6(3)
C(11)-C(12)-C(13)-C(14)	-0.5(4)
S-C(12)-C(13)-C(14)	179.8(2)
C(12)-C(13)-C(15)-C(16)	0.5(3)
C(14)-C(13)-C(15)-C(16)	-179.8(3)
C(13)-C(15)-C(16)-S	-0.2(3)
C(12)-S-C(16)-C(15)	-0.1(2)

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms

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